

“QUALITATIVE AND QUANTITATIVE EVALUATION OF THE USE OF TWITTER AS A TOOL OF ANTIMICROBIAL STEWARDSHIP”

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Abstract

Introduction: Social media networks have transformed the sources of information, including health information. In particular, the microblogging service Twitter has been used as a learning tool in the field of medicine as well as a tool for disease surveillance and outbreak management. As antimicrobial resistance is one of the biggest concerns of public health, we aimed to review how Twitter is being used as a tool for antimicrobial stewardship (AMS).

Methods: We used the software Kampal Social® to collect, analyse and monitor tweets from the whole Twitter network to assess the activity that takes place about antibiotics. The study was carried out in three phases: data acquisition, during which we collected data over a six-month period (from 21 September 2016 to 8 February 2017) by monitoring selected users, hashtags and keywords that we knew to be related to AMS; data cleansing, which involved identifying users who were not related to the topic, thus creating a new collection process to remove those users and add newly discovered ones; and, finally, data acquisition and analysis (From 1 April 2017 to 7 March 2018), during which we collected data using the new users obtained in the cleansing phase. We qualitatively characterized the most influential users, we analysed the use of hashtags and the flow of information (the most retweeted users and the global network formed by all the users).

Results: Using the tool Kampal Social®, and after a cleansing phase to remove irrelevant information, we worked with a dataset of 1,765,388 tweets. Studying the qualitative characterization of the top-ten influencers, we found that most of them are institutional users, but individual users, such as physicians, and an important medical journal also appeared. Regarding hashtags, ‘#antibiotics’ was the one with the most occurrences. Hashtags follow a regular distribution over time, with some defined peaks connected to important dates and reports about antibiotics. As for the flow of information, we obtained a rather dense network of interconnections formed by all the users who had sent a message, which means that a strong relation exists between the different organizations, professionals and users in general.

Conclusions: Institutions, medical journals and physicians and pharmacists are key opinion leaders in the topic of antibiotics, so they must incorporate social media into their communication strategy to spread the AMS message. More evidence is needed regarding the optimal method of communication to spread information throughout the general population. The development of tools capable of collecting and querying large amounts of Twitter data helped us to assess the impact of antibiotic awareness campaigns and to gain an idea of how Twitter is being used to spread the message about AMS.

1. Introduction

The development of social media networks has transformed the paradigm of information dissemination. It has provided pioneering communication opportunities, since users can engage and be content creators rather than simply being recipients of information. In recent years, social networking sites (SNSs) have grown rapidly in popularity. In 2018, it was reported that 69% of American adults use social networking platforms [1]. In particular, the microblogging service Twitter has a population of 342 million active users, who send around 400 million tweets every day [2,3].

Twitter presents itself as an easy-to-use tool to spread information widely as well as a powerful instrument for collecting information in real time. This ability has been used as a tool to share health information. For example, Thackeray et al. found that Twitter is being used as a one-way communication tool to spread messages about breast cancer, particularly general awareness and fundraising [4]. But social media are not only used as a one-way communication, but also as a global source of information. Love et al. studied the use of Twitter as a source of vaccination information [5]. They found that health-focused sites, professional media, and medical organizations dominated shared links, what suggests that users apply some level of critical thinking when evaluating medical content based on their source credibility. Given the ability of Twitter to allowing

connection, engagement, learning and education in real time on a global scale, it can be used as a learning tool. In fact, this purpose has grown during recent years in the field of medicine, since it may constitute a valuable complement to traditional, filed, work-based investigation [6–8]. Twitter is also a valuable tool for public health. Some publications have shown that it is possible to integrate this novel data source on target populations for intervention into disease surveillance and outbreak management [9,10]. This ability was demonstrated during the 2014 Ebola outbreak, when there were more than 10 million tweets in 3 weeks from 170 countries mentioning the word ‘Ebola’ [11]. In fact, Odlum et al studied the use of Twitter as a real-time method of ebola outbreak surveillance [12]. They collected tweets during the 2014 Ebola outbreak, and they found that tweets mentioning “Ebola” were disseminated to 9,362,267,048 people. Their findings demonstrate the usefulness of Twitter mining to inform public health education. A review of the social media use in the Ebola outbreak showed positive results for social media use in effective surveillance response mechanisms for improving the detection, preparedness and response of the outbreak [13]. Also, Twitter has been used for influenza surveillance, in fact, it has shown some usefulness in predicting influenza cases [14,15]. These data show that social media could become a useful tool to complement the information of infodemiological tools.

Among the current global public health problems, antimicrobial resistance has been cited by the WHO (World Health Organization) as one of the top threats to human health [16,17]. Antimicrobial stewardship (AMS) contributes to improving antimicrobial use through programmed activities and interventions [18]. The most important element identified in antimicrobial prescribing has been behavioral. Education is a crucial first step in the change of behavior, so educating primary prescribers and the global population in the optimization of antimicrobials is an essential objective of AMS. As Twitter allows connection, engagement, learning and education in real time on a global scale, it could

constitute a valuable tool for spreading information on AMS. As it has been observed that people across the globe talk about antibiotics on social media, there is a need to understand the contribution and impact of social media tools on public health campaigns about AMS [19].

We claim that characterizing the discourse taking place on Twitter with regard to antibiotics is an important step in evaluating the way in which it is being used to raise awareness of antimicrobial resistance, to monitor the impact of campaigns and to know the real concerns of populations relating to the use of antibiotics. To our knowledge, there has been limited detailed analysis of how and when people talk about antibiotics on social media [20]. Dyar et al analysed the occurrences of the word “antibiotic” in Twitter [21]. They concluded that more evidence is still needed regarding the individuals best suited to post messages. Studies in other fields [6] incorporate the analysis of “*influencers*”. These influencers are the most influential Twitter users on their field, and identifying them is an essential step in any public-health intervention because can be considered the individuals best suited to post messages.

We aimed to review how Twitter is being used as a tool for AMS. We undertook a detailed characterization of the most influential Twitter users (influencers) who focus their discourse on AMS. We also studied the impact of the most influential ‘hashtags’ related to AMS, connecting events with an increase/decrease in their popularity. Finally, we analysed the flow of information between the users and the interaction among them and their audience.

2. Methods

We used Kampal Social [22], a software tool that allows the collection of tweets from the whole Twitter network as well as the monitoring and analysis of the properties of the information collected, to study the activity that takes place on Twitter concerning antibiotics. Kampal Social is a tool developed by Kampal Data Solutions, a spin-off of the University of Zaragoza. It is a commercial product but, for research purposes, it can be used for free. This application is based on recent developments in the area of complex networks, which put the emphasis on the characteristics of networks (topology) to complement the classical statistical approach, which do not take into account the interactions between constituents of the system. The mention of each other in a tweet, or the fact of having retweeted the message of another user, can be used to establish a relationship and construct the network. Once the network is generated, complex network algorithms position the nodes according to the strength of the relationships, achieving a global vision of what is happening, and provide different types of results such as communities of users, measures of centrality or importance of the nodes, etc.

The study was carried out in three phases: data acquisition, data cleansing and final data acquisition and analysis. Each of these phases is explained below (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Study phases

2.1. First phase: Data acquisition

We collected tweets using the tool Kampal Social® during a six-month period (from 21 September 2016 to 8 February 2017) by monitoring a working list of users and hashtags (Table 1). This working list was obtained in two phases:

Firstly, we selected users and hashtags that we knew were related to antibiotics according to our experience and after the revision of published evidence about Twitter users related to antibiotic field [23].

Secondly, as we also wanted to identify other unknown users with potentially influential opinions, we decided to monitor Twitter activity using keywords that we knew were related to AMS according to our experience (mainly hashtags, but they could simply be a string forming part of the tweet). Thus, we collected tweets from the entire Twitter network, containing any of the keywords proposed, so that we could identify hidden users posting about the same topic.

Table 1. Selected user names and keywords used to collect tweets related to AMS during the first phase of the study

Users	Hashtags
@proa_hcuz, @proamacarena, @proa_hulp, @proa_maran, @proahupm, @proa_psmar, @proa_alicante, @guiaprioam, @stgamicrobial, @asteamroma1_sfn, @amsinsigth, @esgap_abs, @ncas_aus, @idpharmd, @sapgabx, @southafricanasp, @antibioticleeds, @jhorcajada, @duke_aset, @belenpadi, @jesusbano, @brxad, @abpreservation, @rafamcanton, @cddep, @eaad_eu, @dan_uslan, @idstewardship, @standeresinsky, @calderwoodmd, @joserrapa, @mshuhnasp, @leonorperianez, @idpharmprof, @abxstewardship, @raseaton66, @aempsgob, @grupo_afinf_sef	antibiotic resistance, antimicrobial resistance, antimicrobial stewardship, antimicrobial AND stewardship, antimicrobials, asp, ams, optimización AND antibióticos, antibioticguardian, antibioticstewardship, optimizacion AND antibioticos, antibioticos, abxstewardship, antibiotics, antibiotic AND stewardship, antimicrobialstewardship, antibióticos, saveabx, proa, eaad, antibiotic AND awareness, waad, antibioticresistance, waaw, waaw AND antimicrobial, waaw AND antibiotic, actonamr, combatingamr, prudente AND antibiotico, prudente AND antibiótico, prudente AND antibióticos, prudente AND antibioticos, geih16

2.2. Second phase: Data cleansing

One of the biggest difficulties one faces when analysing Twitter data (or any other information obtained from social networks) is to filter the information in order to remove the unrelated contents while maintaining most of the data related to the project under study. Generally, this cannot be done in a completely automatic way. It requires some human supervision to do it in a precise way.

After collecting the data, we detected that certain users, with an enormous number of mentions, were not related to the topic. Table 2 presents the Top-10 users with a higher number of mentions in the set of collected tweets. We can observe that several of them do not belong to the domain of neither antibiotics nor healthcare. So we decided to carry out a cleansing phase to exclude those users we consider irrelevant (e.g. Youtube, PerdueChicken, KLM, etc.) for the study and keep the promising ones (e.g. WHO, AEMPSGOB, idPharmd, etc.).

For this cleansing phase, we collected the first 100 users with more retweets, hashtags and mentions. We analyzed their Twitter profile one by one to check if they were related to the topic. The use of complex networks facilitates the identification of the unrelated users, as they appear in areas of the network that are practically unconnected to its core, formed by the users that are really related to the subject of the study. If the users were not related, we removed them from Kampal® in order to get only real users talking about antibiotics.

As the result of the data cleansing, we removed the users not related to the topic and discovered some new with Twitter conversations about AMS and antibiotics that were not being monitored in this initial stage. Thus, we created a new collection process with a set of users that contained the users being monitored in the initial phase (Table 1, left side) along with the new ones discovered in the cleansing phase (Table 3).

User	Definition	# mentions
YouTube	Video platform	10,495
PerdueChicken	Brand of food industry	7,665
AEMPSGOB	Spanish agency of medicines and health products	3,501
KLM	Royal Dutch airline	2,996
WHO	World Health Organization	2,817
Idpharmd	Pharmacist	2,251
c0nvey	Promote Twitter account	2,200
IDstewardship	Pharmacist	2,076
LNBofficiel	French national basketball league	1,890
sigstrasbourg	French basketball professional club	1,801

Table 2. Top-10 users with a higher number of mentions (most of them are not related to AMS)

New relevant users
@DrFriedenCDC, @JGPharmD, @idpharmd, @jonotter, @eliowa, @kevinmd, @LauraPiddock, @DidierPittet, @dan_uslan, @peds_id_doc, @DoctorNatasha, @IDDocHymes, @JasonGNewland, @SeattleMamaDoc, @ICHEJournal, @TheLancetInfDis, @JAMA_current, @NEJM, @InfectDisNews, @MedscapeID, @NIAIDNews, @AMSnewsroom, @APUANews, @Peds_ID, @NFIDvaccines, @CDCFlu, @CDC_HIVAIDS, @cdchep, @WHO, @ASM microbiology, @SHEA_Epi, @BSACandJAC, @TheUrgentNeed, @IDSainfo, @APIC, @PIDSociety, @SHARPSgroup, @PeggyFund, @cdiffFoundation, @saveantibiotics

Table 3. New relevant users discovered in the data-cleansing phase

2.3. Third phase: Final data acquisition and data analysis

From 1 April 2017 to 7 March 2018, we collected data using the new data obtained during the cleansing phase, excluding noisy users and hashtags.

Following the data collection, we wanted to know who the most influential users were.

We defined the influencers according to their number of mentions. There are several indicators that could be used as a proxy to the relevance of a user, such as the number of followers, number of tweets generated, mentions received, retweets of his/her messages, centrality in the network, among others. However, most of them are not very suitable to define, by themselves, which are the main influencers for our study. The number of followers may be not indicative of the user relevance for a particular subject, like this one. The number of tweets generated is indicative of the activity of the user, but not of the influence he/she produces on the rest of people (and can be adulterated by bots).

Measures of centrality are good indicators of the ability of a user to communicate different regions of the network (betweenness) or about the relevance of a node in a more local environment, in a network sense (page rank); however, they may not provide a direct estimation of the user global influence. Retweets and mentions do provide a more direct indication of the interest that the messages of a user arouse among the people. To make a retweet, however, is a very easy act, while to make a mention is a more conscious one

and it requires an effort. In fact, an only successful message can get a lot of retweets almost instantaneously, while to have a lot of mentions can be more indicative of the influence of the author. As a consequence, we have selected the number of mentions to define the influencers of our study.

After obtaining the top-ten influencers, we characterized them qualitatively according to the kind of user (individual, organization or institutional), country, joining date and first language used.

We also assessed the use of hashtags. We identified the most popular ones and focused especially on the temporality of hashtags, connecting dates related to antibiotics with peaks occurring in the temporality of hashtags.

To study the flow of information, we analysed the more retweeted users and the global network formed by all the users who have sent a message within the framework of this study. Accordingly, we defined a link between each pair of nodes (users), which was weighted by the number of mentions between them, and we borrowed several techniques from the complex network field to represent and analyse the network formed in this way [24]. To represent the network graphically as a position map, we used force-directed algorithms [25] and a Monte Carlo process to separate overlapping nodes, obtaining graphs in which users with more interaction (i.e. those with more mentions between them) are closer. These provided a geometrical vision of the network, which is useful for identifying groups of users with stronger internal relations and fewer or weaker relations outside the group, corresponding to the intuitive concept of communities. The users forming the communities were named members. To make a precise determination of these communities in an automatic way, we used Walktrap [26] and leading-eigenvector algorithms. Walktrap algorithm works on dense subgraphs of sparse graphs (communities), which appear in most real-world complex networks, and play an

important role in many contexts. Through comparing similarities between nodes in random walks, Walktrap is able to capture community structures in a network, in an efficient way.

Over this network, one can also define different kinds of centrality measures to quantify the most cohesive nodes or those with the greatest authority. We further calculated the betweenness [27,28], which provides an indication of the importance of a node to connect different communities.

3. Results

Using the tool Kampal®, we analysed more than 5 million data, including tweets, retweets, mentions, replies and users. Table 4 summarizes the collected data.

Key performance indicators	First data acquisition	Final data acquisition
Tweets from all users	1,404,511	1,765,388
Retweets among all users	1,160,495	2,775,737
Mentions among all users	657,909	2,066,113
Replies from all users	273,599	488,767
Users	1,349,877	1,839,705

Table 4. Summary data of the first and third phases of the study (excluding the cleansing phase)

We obtained the ‘influencers’ and characterized them qualitatively. The results obtained are summarized in Table 5.

User	Mentions	Kind of user	Country	Example of tweet
WHO	308,993	Institutional (World Health Organization)	Switzerland	November 10 th 2017: #antibioticResistance is rising to dangerously high levels in all parts of the world and threatening our ability to treat common infectious diseases bit.ly/2hghRBY
DrTedros	41,438	Individual (Director of WHO)	Switzerland	November, 14 th 2017: It’s World Antibiotic Awareness Week. #AntibioticResistance is a global health crisis that must be addressed with the utmost urgency.

UN	35,666	Institutional (United Nations)	United States	September, 12 nd 2016: Handle antibiotics with care - @WHO info on #AntibioticResistance http://goo.gl/BZRf4n
Kevinmd	29,448	Individual (physician)	United States	May 22 nd 2019: How non-video telehealth can be a cure for overprescribing antibiotics https://buff.ly/2Edu2LP
NEJM	26,751	Corporate (New England Journal of Medicine)	United States	August 23 rd 2017: Should patients complete antibiotic courses to prevent antibiotic resistance? Discuss now in this week's #NEJMForum: http://nej.md/2vXZsSu
WHOAFRO	25,755	Institutional (WHO African Region)	Congo	November 8 th 2017: Use of antibiotics in healthy animals for growth promotion can contribute to #AntibioticResistance. It should be completely restricted.
WHO_Europe	24,400	Institutional (WHO Europe)	Denmark	November 15 th 2018: Respecting antibiotics 🍷 and using them only when strictly necessary is good for people AND sheep 🐑 Human and animal health are #onehealth. http://bit.ly/2Dj16F4 #AntibioticResistance #StopDrugResistance
WHOSEARO	22,446	Institutional (WHO South- East Asia)	India	January 9 th 2019: #Antibiotics cure infections, but for years we have taken too many of them & often for the flu, for which they do not work. This has made many bacteria resistant, which means that antibiotics will no longer work. Help prevent #antimicrobialresistance by following these rules (video)
WHOEMRO	22,076	Institutional (WHO Mediterranean Region)	Egypt	January 29 th 2018: WHO GLASS report shows widespread #antibiotic resistance to common bacterial infections like #E. coli, #Staph and #Salmonella. #StopSuperbugs http://bit.ly/2nnFvz4
pahowho	21,925	Institutional (WHO Inter- American System)	Americas	November 16 th 2018: Antibiotics save millions of lives all over the world, but we are currently experiencing exceptional rates of resistance. New guide for managing #AntibioticResistance programs in

				Latin America and the Caribbean: https://bit.ly/2qQqMi5
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Table 5. Characterization of the top-ten influencers

Regarding the use of hashtags, Table 6 summarizes the top-ten hashtags, which were most commonly used in the collected tweets.

Hashtag	Description	Occurrences
antibiotics	-	447,852
Ams	Antimicrobial Stewardship	290,090
ASP	Antimicrobial Stewardship Program	178,008
antibioticos	Antibiotics in Spanish	150,933
PROA	Programa de Optimización del uso de Antibióticos	53,371
waaw	World Antibiotic Awareness Week	51,290
antibioticresistance	-	45,191
AntibioticResistance	-	22,802
antimicrobialresistance	-	15,189
waad	European Antibiotic Awareness Day	14,168

Table 6. Most frequently used hashtags

We also focused on the temporality of the hashtags. Some of them are constantly present in the network, while others have a temporary popularity. In Figure 2, we show the evolution in the use of different hashtags over the monitored time period.

Figure 2. Use of hashtags through time (in number of occurrences) from April 2017 to March 2018. * Drop due to a maintenance stop of the datacenter

As regards the analysis of the flow of information, firstly we analysed the number of retweets obtained by different users (Table 7).

User	Retweets
WHO	560,597
NEJM	100,033
JAMA_current	54,039
UN	21,935
CDCFlu	20,674

Table 7. Most retweeted users on the topic of antibiotics (WHO: World Health Organization; NEJM: New England Journal of Medicine; JAMA_current: scientific journal JAMA; UN: United Nations, CDCFlu: flu-related updates from the Center for Disease Control and Prevention)

We also analysed the flow of information between the users. Figure 3 shows a representation of the network formed by all the users who had sent a message within the framework of this study (each point of the network is a Twitter user, not only the selected users but any institutional or private user who has issued a message in the frame of the study). For the sake of clarity, we only show the 1,000 users with the largest number of mentions. We show the position on the network of the top 10 influencers, observing that most of them are in the scope of the UN/WHO organizations, except NEJM and kevinmd.

Figure 3. Global network of Twitter users in the context of antibiotics. The communities' partition has been calculated with the Walktrap algorithm and it presents a modularity score of 0.47. The legend on the right shows the colour of each community. The lower part of the figure shows a zoom of the two areas of the network where the top 10 influencers are present.

In the network, the different colours of the nodes correspond to the different communities detected automatically, using the algorithms cited above. If one gives to each community the name of the most mentioned user belonging to it, one finds that the main communities of the network are the following:

1. WHO. A community mainly led by world organizations related to health, their representatives and doctors.
2. SIDPharm. This community is mainly formed by pharmacy associations and professionals.
3. Kevinmd. This includes physicians relevant to social media as well as scientific reviews of the health field.
4. WHOAFRO. Mainly regional and national health organizations.
5. AntibioticLeeds. A community led by Philip Howard, a pharmacist in Leeds, mainly formed by United Kingdom organizations and professionals.
6. CdiffFoundation. Community led by the Clostridium Difficile Infections Foundation and mainly consisting of doctors from the Indian community.
7. AEMPSGOB. A Spanish community led by the Spanish Agency of Medicines.
8. MoHFW_INDIA. Indian organizations and professionals.
9. Alemuw1. A community led by the WHO representative in Nigeria and mainly formed by Nigerian organizations and professionals.

The graph shows a rather dense network of interconnections, which means that a strong relation (mentions) exists among the different organizations, professionals and users in general. Table 8 analyses the number of mentions of each community.

Community name	Total mentions	Internal mentions (within the community)	Number of members
WHO	26,147	19,104	277
SIDPharm	23,660	21,365	170
kevinmd	8,524	7,473	80
WHOAFRO	8,345	5,805	64
AntibioticLeeds	6,679	5,327	66
cdiffFoundation	6,375	6,296	11
AEMPSGOB	2,899	2,792	40
MoHFW_INDIA	1,893	1,782	38
alemuw1	1,208	1,093	21

Table 8. Total mentions made by each community

The more central nodes according to their betweenness are shown in Table 9. The top is dominated by the health organizations @WHO and @WHOAFRO, but a number of researchers or professionals in the pharmacy world, such as @IDstewardship, @idpharmd, @khalideljaaly, @elizbeech and @DrDianeAshiru, also appear. A graphical representation of the centrality of nodes, in terms of betweenness, is presented in Figure 4, in which node size represents a proportional betweenness value. We have exported the data provided by Kampal® and have worked with the Gephi® software in order to highlight weighted edges and show the flow of the information. We use Yifan Hu (2011). algorithms for visualizing the networks.

User	Betweenness
@WHO	1
@WHOAFRO	0.78
@IDstewardship	0.57
@idpharmd	0.55

@khalideljaaly	0.44
@IDSAInfo	0.17
@elizbeech	0.16
@JAMA_current	0.14
@DrDianeAshiru	0.12
@SouthAfricanASP	0.09

Table 9. More central nodes according to betweenness

Figure 3. Network representation highlighting node betweenness and weighted edges

4. Discussion

Using Kampal Social, a software tool that allows the collection of tweets from the Twittersphere, we performed a comprehensive analysis of the Twitter discussion on antibiotics to review how Twitter is being used as a tool for AMS. Firstly, we wanted to know which users act as influencers over others. Several studies show that identifying

key opinion leaders is an essential step in any public-health intervention, especially when using a network-based communication platform [21,29]. The leaders contribute heavily to the community, and they contribute to the critical mass of the conversation, but more importantly the community can rely on these individuals to keep the conversation going [6]. Analysing the qualitative characterization of the top-ten influencers, we found that most of them are institutional users (@WHO, @UN, @WHO_AFRO, @WHO_Europe, @WHOSEARO, @WHOEMRO and @pahowho), two of them are individuals (@DrTedros and @kevinmd) and only one is a corporate user (@NEJM). Most of them are large and important organizations related to health but not specifically connected to AMS. This is reasonable, since large organizations have professionals to operate their Twitter accounts, yet it is encouraging that individual physicians are among the key influencers. It can be noted that none of the influencers is related to the pharmaceutical industry, so it seems that they do not have much influence on social media in this field. Previous work in this area confirmed our findings. For example, the study by Borgmann et al. [30] analysed the activity of Twitter in the field of urology. Their analysis showed that health care organizations were the top influencers for all urological cancers. Additionally, Jacobsen and Jacobsen [31] suggested that awareness campaigns used by health organizations promoted increased detection and diagnosis of breast cancer during the mid-1990s, when the awareness movement was expanding rapidly across the United States. Our study found that not only organizations but also individuals can be top influencers in a Twitter discussion. In fact, Thackeray et al. [4] found that individuals had more retweets and mentions than organizations and celebrities during the Breast Cancer Awareness Month. These studies suggest that institutional organizations must consider social media within their communication strategies to spread the message about AMS but

that individuals can also take part in the discussion, creating the possibility of discussing antibiotics with different stakeholders in the health care sector.

We also studied the most popular antibiotic-related hashtags during the study period and their temporality. We clearly observed that hashtags follow a regular distribution over time. However, we could distinguish some defined peaks that we wanted to explore. For instance, the hashtag ‘antibiotics’ presents a high peak around the end of September 2017. Examining the tweets around that date, we found out that the WHO had issued an important report on the topic on 20 September: ‘Antibacterial agents in clinical development: An analysis of the antibacterial clinical development pipeline, including tuberculosis’ [32]. This report prompted the quick spread of conversations about antibiotics on Twitter. There were also some peaks during the third week of November, when the WHO celebrated the World Antibiotic Awareness Week, including the European Antibiotic Awareness Day on 18 November. We also found that the activity reached in the peaks returned to the basal level in a short period of time. The study by Dyar et al. [21] identified the daily occurrences of the word ‘antibiotic’ during a year, and they also found peaks in the discussion about antibiotics. These peaks were related to announcements and publications by the UK Chief Medical Officer, the USA Food and Drug Administration and the USA Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (CDC). According to our results, the peaks that they found were related to health organization announcements or campaigns, but the activity returned to the basal level prior to the peaks within 48 hours. Other studies proposed that tweets related to breaking news are more likely to be retweeted [33] but have a short-term impact. This suggests the need to find strategies to achieve a more sustained response [34].

To study the information diffusion potential of the promoters of the antibiotic discussion on Twitter, we analysed the most retweeted users, the relation of the users with their

environment and their capacity to connect with others. The users with the most retweets were @WHO, @NEJM and @UN. This is reasonable, since the greater the popularity, the higher the likelihood of greater dissemination [35], but, among the most retweeted users, we also found @CDC_Flu and @JAMA_current, who are not included in our top-ten influencers. This is encouraging, since not only key opinion leaders but a variety of voices from the antibiotics field can successfully spread the message about AMS. Besides, @JAMA_current is an important medical journal, which shows the potential of these journals to spread their scientific content among a larger audience through the use of Twitter. This result agrees with the study by Pemmaraju et al. [36] in the field of the haematology. They analysed the hashtag #MPNSM (myeloproliferative neoplasms on social media) during a two-year period. They found that the six most common retweets were generated by six different users, encompassing health care stakeholders from all over their field, consisting of a medical journal, a patient, a medical society, a university, a physician and an organization.

Analysing the relation between the users, we obtained nine communities, of which the WHO and SIDPharm communities occupy a central position in the network, indicative of a prominent role in the communication of this subject on Twitter, while the communities that are less connected to the rest are those of CdiffFoundation and AEMPSGOB (in the last case, this is probably due to the use of the Spanish language). Taking part in these communities, we found health organizations, doctors and pharmacists and quality academic journals. These interconnections evidence the large information diffusion potential of Twitter to spread the message about antibiotics by different stakeholders related to the health care sector. The betweenness also shows that some users who do not have an extremely large number of followers (between 2,000 and 9,000 approximately) occupy a central position in the network and connect different groups of users. These

measures allow identifying relevant users which play an essential role in the information dissemination. Regarding how this might be used for public health, from a managerial point of view, identifying influential nodes might help to improve the dissemination of important information about AMS to a wider audience. Mishori et al. [35] also determined the information diffusion potential on Twitter of four medical networks: the American Medical Association, the American Academy of Family Physicians, the American Academy of Pediatrics and the American College of Physicians. During their study period, each network had thousands of followers and information dissemination potential ranging from 6.9 to 122 million people. This gives us an idea of how Twitter is being used to spread health care information between a variety of voices in the field of the health care sector, including organizations, institutions and professionals. It is true that, in our study, we did not find any members of the general population or patients as users in the above communities. Maybe the health care community has to focus on expanding its audience to the general population, because it seems that the message only reaches users related to health care sectors.

The use of Twitter is becoming a standard mean of communication in the field of health information. Hence, health care professionals are supposed to acquire skills in the use of social media to spread medical information and to be up to date [37]. But not only the use of social networks, but also the analysis of the information generated in social media conversations is increasingly relevant. The analysis of this information is demonstrating to be useful not only to know how conversation about health in the Web is going on, but also to elucidate errors in published medical information [38], identify factors that promote the dissemination of information [39,40] or detect certain health trends in groups of patients [41]. The analysis of the health information generated in social networks requires multidisciplinary work between health care professionals and professionals

specialized in data analysis tools, as Kampal Social®. Other tools have been used to analyse social media data, as Symplur® [6,30], Sysosmos® [42], Hive® [19], or Topsy® [21]. The development of tools capable of collecting and querying large amounts of Twitter data helped us to assess the impact of antibiotic awareness campaigns and to gain an idea of how Twitter is being used to spread the message about AMS.

To our knowledge, this is the first study to attempt to characterize simultaneously the users, discussion and flow of information about antibiotics on Twitter. Our study analysed the most influential users in the field of antibiotics, and the information diffusion potential of the promoters of the antibiotic discussion on Twitter, which had not been published before. We think that an important strength of this study is the conducting of a data-cleansing phase to remove unrelated data and enable us to monitor users, hashtags and keywords that are really related to AMS. However, these results should be interpreted according to the following limitations. Firstly, during the first period of study, the users and keywords that we monitored were obtained by experience, so it is possible that we produced a bias, since we could not find all the existent users and hashtags related to AMS. Secondly, the data-cleansing phase was carried out by hand, so we could identify Twitter data that really interested us. Finally, we think that it would be interesting to make a qualitative classification of the tweets to obtain the more popular topics of AMS discussed on Twitter. Future work including this classification would be very interesting in this field.

In conclusion, Twitter is a tool used by different stakeholders in the health care sector to spread information about AMS. Global organizations, such as the WHO but also medical journals and physicians and pharmacists, are key opinion leaders, so they must consider social media within their communication strategy to spread the AMS message. We found that Twitter has information diffusion potential to spread the message about antibiotics

between health care-related users, but more evidence is needed regarding the optimal method of communication to disseminate information to the general population.

In future studies, we plan to consider the use of other social media platforms, possibly along with other analysis tools, to explore the effect of possible bias derived from the popularity of each platform in different segments of the society (e.g. age, job, etc.) For instance, Instagram user age range is different to the one in Twitter or Facebook, and this is an issue that could be taken into consideration in any information dissemination campaign.

5. Summary table

What was already known	What this study added to our knowledge
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Twitter has been used to spread messages about medicine and public health, but to our knowledge, there has been limited detailed analysis of how and when people talk about antibiotics. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - This is the first study that characterizes the users, discussion and flow of information about antibiotics on Twitter. - Global organizations, medical journals and physicians and pharmacists must consider social media within their communication strategy. - More evidence is needed regarding the optimal method of communication to disseminate information to the general population.

6. Abbreviations

AMS: antimicrobial stewardship

ASP: antimicrobial stewardship programme

CDC: Centre for Disease Prevention and Control

NEJM: New England Journal of Medicine

Pahowho: World Health Organization Inter-American System

PROA: programa de optimización de uso de antimicrobianos

SNSs: social networking sites

UK: United Kingdom

UN: United Nations

WAAW: World Antibiotic Awareness Week

WHO: World Health Organization

WHOAFRO: World Health Organization African Region

WHO_Europe: World Health Organization Europe

WHOSEARO: World Health Organization South-East Asia

WHOEMRO: World Health Organization Mediterranean Region

7. Declaration of Conflicting interests

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

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9. References

1. Demographics of Social Media Users and Adoption in the United States | Pew

- Research Center [Internet]. [cited 2018 Feb 21]. Available from:
<http://www.pewinternet.org/fact-sheet/social-media/>
2. Twitter by the Numbers (2017): Stats, Demographics & Fun Facts [Internet]. [cited 2017 Nov 14]. Available from:
<https://www.omnicoreagency.com/twitter-statistics/>
 3. STATS | Twitter Company Statistics – Statistic Brain [Internet]. [cited 2017 Nov 14]. Available from: <https://www.statisticbrain.com/twitter-statistics/>
 4. Thackeray R, Burton SH, Giraud-Carrier C, Rollins S, Draper CR. Using Twitter for breast cancer prevention: an analysis of breast cancer awareness month. *BMC Cancer*. 2013;13(1):508.
 5. Love B, Himmelboim I, Holton A, Stewart K. Twitter as a source of vaccination information: Content drivers and what they are saying. *Am J Infect Control*. 2013;41(6):568–70.
 6. Jalali A, Sherbino J, Frank J, Sutherland S. Social media and medical education: Exploring the potential of Twitter as a learning tool. *Int Rev Psychiatry*. 2015;27(2):140–6.
 7. Rouprêt M, Misraï V. Utilisation exponentielle des réseaux sociaux en médecine: Exemple de l'intérêt de Twitter© en urologie. *Prog en Urol*. 2015;25(1):11–7.
 8. Roberts MJ, Perera M, Lawrentschuk N, Romanic D, Papa N, Bolton D. Globalization of continuing professional development by journal clubs via microblogging: a systematic review. *J Med Internet Res*. 2015;17(4):e103.
 9. Collier N, Son NT, Nguyen NM. OMG U got flu? Analysis of shared health messages for bio-surveillance. *CEUR Workshop Proc*. 2010;714(5):18–26.
 10. Charles-Smith LE, Reynolds TL, Cameron MA, Conway M, Lau EHY, Olsen JM, et al. Using social media for actionable disease surveillance and outbreak

- management: A systematic literature review. *PLoS One*. 2015;10(10):1–20.
11. #Ebola - Healthcare Social Media Analytics and Transcripts [Internet]. [cited 2017 Nov 14]. Available from: <https://www.symplur.com/healthcare-hashtags/ebola/>
 12. Odium M, Yoon S. What can we learn about the Ebola outbreak from tweets? *Am J Infect Control*. 2015;43(6):563–71.
 13. Hossain L, Kam D, Kong F, Wigand Rt, Bossomaier T. Social media in Ebola outbreak. *Epidemiol Infect*. 2016;144(10):2136–43.
 14. Nagar R, Yuan Q, Freifeld CC, Santillana M, Nojima A, Chunara R, et al. A Case Study of the New York City 2012-2013 Influenza Season With Daily Geocoded Twitter Data From Temporal and Spatiotemporal Perspectives. *J Med Internet Res*. 2014;16(10):e236.
 15. Hartley DM, Giannini CM, Wilson S, Frieder O, Margolis PA, Kotagal UR, et al. Coughing, sneezing, and aching online: Twitter and the volume of influenza-like illness in a pediatric hospital. *PLoS One*. 2017;12(7):1–10.
 16. WHO | World Health Day 2011. WHO [Internet]. 2011 [cited 2018 Feb 24]; Available from: http://www.who.int/mediacentre/news/releases/2011/whd_20110406/en/
 17. WHO | The world is running out of antibiotics, WHO report confirms. WHO [Internet]. 2017 [cited 2018 Feb 24]; Available from: <http://www.who.int/mediacentre/news/releases/2017/running-out-antibiotics/en/>
 18. Rodríguez-Baño J, Paño-Pardo JR, Alvarez-Rocha L, Asensio Á, Calbo E, Cercenado E, et al. Programas de optimización de uso de antimicrobianos (PROA) en hospitales españoles: documento de consenso GEIH-SEIMC, SEFH y SEMSPH. *Enferm Infecc Microbiol Clin*. 2012;30(1):22.e1-22.e23.

19. Kendra RL, Karki S, Eickholt JL, Gandy L. Characterizing the discussion of antibiotics in the Twittersphere: What is the bigger picture? *J Med Internet Res.* 2015;17(6):e154.
20. Scanfeld D, Scanfeld V, Larson EL. Dissemination of health information through social networks: Twitter and antibiotics. *Am J Infect Control.* 2010;38(3):182–8.
21. Dyar OJ, Castro-Sánchez E, Holmes AH. What makes people talk about antibiotics on social media? A retrospective analysis of Twitter use. *J Antimicrob Chemother.* 2014;69(9):2568–72.
22. Kampal Social [Internet]. [cited 2018 Aug 29]. Available from: <http://social.kampal.com/>
23. Goff DA, Van Den Bergh D. Twitter: A tool to improve healthcare professionals' awareness of antimicrobial resistance and antimicrobial stewardship. *South African Med J.* 2015;105(5):427–30.
24. Boccaletti S, Latora V, Moreno Y, Chavez M, Hwang D-U. Complex networks: Structure and dynamics. *Phys Rep.* 2006;424(4):175–308.
25. Fruchterman TMJ, Reingold EM. Graph Drawing by Force-directed Placement. *Softw Pr Exper.* 1991;21(11):1129–64.
26. Pons P, Latapy M. Computing Communities in Large Networks Using Random Walks. In: *Proceedings of the 20th International Conference on Computer and Information Sciences.* Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer-Verlag; 2005. p. 284–93. (ISCIS'05).
27. Hu, Y. (2011). Algorithms for visualizing large networks. *Combinatorial Scientific Computing*, 5(3), 180-186.
28. Freeman LC. A Set of Measures of Centrality Based on Betweenness. *Sociometry.* 1977;40(1):35–41.

29. Newman MEJ. A measure of betweenness centrality based on random walks. *Soc Networks*. 2005;27.
30. Bodendorf F, Kaiser C. Detecting opinion leaders and trends in online social networks. In: *Proceeding of the 2nd ACM workshop on Social web search and mining - SWSM '09*. New York, New York, USA: ACM Press; 2009. Available from: <http://portal.acm.org/citation.cfm?doid=1651437.1651448>
31. Borgmann H, Loeb S, Salem J, Thomas C, Haferkamp A, Murphy DG, et al. Activity, content, contributors, and influencers of the twitter discussion on urologic oncology. *Urol Oncol Semin Orig Investig*. 2016;34(9):377–83.
32. Jacobsen GD, Jacobsen KH. Health awareness campaigns and diagnosis rates: Evidence from National Breast Cancer Awareness Month. *J Health Econ*. 2011 Jan;30(1):55–61.
33. Antibacterial agents in clinical development [Internet]. [cited 2018 Sep 10]. Available from: <http://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/258965/WHO-EMP-IAU-2017.11-eng.pdf;jsessionid=5D10CEC317067CB86E449B6ADBC4370B?sequence=1>
34. Naveed N, Gottron T, Arifah JK, Alhadi C. Bad News Travel Fast: A Content-based Analysis of Interestingness on Twitter. [cited 2018 Jul 12]; Available from: <http://tw.rpi.edu/media/latest/WebSciPAper50.pdf>
35. Zaman T, Fox EB, Bradlow ET. A bayesian approach for predicting the popularity of tweets. *Ann Appl Stat*. 2014;8(3):1583–611.
36. Mishori R, Singh LO, Levy B, Newport C. Mapping physician Twitter networks: describing how they work as a first step in understanding connectivity, information flow, and message diffusion. *J Med Internet Res*. 2014;16(4):e107.
37. Pemmaraju N, Utengen A, Gupta V, Kiladjian JJ, Mesa R, Thompson MA. Rare

- Cancers and Social Media: Analysis of Twitter Metrics in the First 2 Years of a Rare-Disease Community for Myeloproliferative Neoplasms on Social Media—#MPNSM. *Curr Hematol Malig Rep.* 2017;12(6):598–604.
38. Debra A Goff, Ravina Kullar, Ramanan Laxminarayan, Marc Mendelson, Dilip Nathwani, Michael Osterholm. Twitter to engage, educate, and advocate for global antibiotic stewardship and antimicrobial resistance. *The Lancet Infectious Diseases* 2019;19(3):229-231.
 39. Edwards S, Roland D Learning from mistakes on social media *Emergency Medicine Journal.* 2019;36:453-455.
 40. Mitchell, B., Russo, P., Otter, J., Kiernan, M., & Aveling, L. What Makes a Tweet Fly? Analysis of Twitter Messaging at Four Infection Control Conferences. *Infection Control & Hospital Epidemiology.*2017;38(11):1271-1276.
 41. Jayaram M, Adams CE, Friedel JS, et al Day of the week to tweet: a randomised controlled trial. *BMJ Open.* 2019;9:e025380.
 42. Gunaratne K, Coomes E, Haghbayan H. Temporal trends in anti-vaccine discourse on Twitter. *Vaccine.* 2019;37(35):4867-4871.
 43. Andersen B, Hair L, Groshek J, Krishna A, Walker D. Understanding and Diagnosing Antimicrobial Resistance on Social Media: A Yearlong Overview of Data and Analytics. *Health Commun.* 2019 Feb;34(2):248-25.